

APPENDIX – Mapping of C2M practices and factors from secondary studies

Table 1 – DSD communication process factors by category

Categories	Factors (F1- F29)	References: ES – Secondary Studies (ES_01 – ES_23)	Number of Studies (%) / Quality
C1. Human Factors	F1. Cultural differences	ES_02; ES_04; ES_05; ES_11; ES_14; ES_16; ES_17; ES_20.	8/20 (40%)
	F3. Language / Language Barriers	ES_03; ES_04; ES_05; ES_11; ES_14; ES_15; ES_18.	7/20 (35%)
	F5. Coordination	ES_02; ES_05; ES_09; ES_16; ES_17; ES_18.	6/20 (30%)
	F6. Visibility/Perception	ES_02; ES_03; ES_11; ES_12; ES_17; ES_18.	6/20 (30%)
	F7. Limited Informal Communication	ES_02; ES_03; ES_05; ES_15; ES_16; ES_18.	6/20 (30%)
	F17. Team Awareness	ES_02; ES_12.	2/20 (10%)
	F18. Communication Skills	ES_02; ES_18.	2/20 (10%)
	F19. Reduced Contact Networks	ES_02; ES_17.	2/20 (10%)
	F20. Definition of roles and responsibilities	ES_17; ES_18.	2/20 (10%)
	F27. Size of Personal Networks	ES_02.	1/20 (5%)
F29. Weak Social Relations	ES_05.	1/20 (5%)	
C2. Location and Infrastructure	F2. Geographical Dispersion	ES_03; ES_04; ES_05; ES_11; ES_12; ES_15; ES_18.	7/20 (35%)
	F4. Time distance	ES_05; ES_06; ES_11; ES_15; ES_18; ES_19.	6/20 (30%)
	F8. Infrastructure	ES_02; ES_05; ES_07; ES_11; ES_15.	5/20 (25%)
	F9. Absence of face-to-face interaction	ES_04; ES_05; ES_15; ES_18; ES_20.	5/20 (25%)
	F21. Synchronization of Working Hours	ES_06.	1/20 (5%)

C3. Processes and Technology	F10. Definition of Communication Media (synchronous and asynchronous)	ES_03; ES_05; ES_15; ES_17; ES_18.	5/20 (25%)
	F11. Applying Agile Approaches	ES_07; ES_16; ES_18; ES_19.	4/20 (20%)
	F12. Selection of Communication Technologies	ES_02; ES_05; ES_08; ES_18.	4/20 (20%)
	F13. Task distribution	ES_02; ES_05; ES_16; ES_18.	4/20 (20%)
	F14. Collaboration Tools	ES_02; ES_06; ES_14; ES_18.	4/20 (20%)
	F15. High Bandwidth	ES_05, ES_06.	2/20 (10%)
	F16. Communication Standards	ES_02; ES_05.	2/20 (10%)
	F22. Number of Distributed Teams	ES_01.	1/20 (5%)
	F23. Communication Policies	ES_06.	1/20 (5%)
	F24. Different Styles of Communication	ES_03.	1/20 (5%)
	F25. Collaboration Models	ES_10.	1/20 (5%)
	F26. Multiple Communication Channels	ES_06.	1/20 (5%)
	F28. Translation and Coding Process	ES_02.	1/20 (5%)

Source: Own Preparation, with data from the systematic tertiary study

F1. Cultural differences

- **ES_02** – *“Cultural differences imply different terminologies which may cause mistakes in messages and translation errors.”* (ES_02, F1, 6, 2°)
- **ES_04** – *“Due to different cultures and languages in outsourcing business it is quite possible that a message is misunderstood by one or more of the outsourcing parties.”* (ES_04, F1, 83, 6°)
- **ES_05** – *“Mutual trust is important but hard to obtain in GDSPs. This can be due to lack of face-a-face interaction cultural differences and weak social relations. Trust among stakeholders is necessary to achieve innovation, flexibility, cooperation, and efficiency in a distributed environment.”* (ES_05, F1, 513, 3°)
- **ES_11** – *“Cultural differences, issues of trust, differences in knowledge levels, and language barriers are cited as causes of poor or ineffective communication, as well as the lack of synchronous communication. Too much information generated by e-mail and frequent conference calls was also identified as source of low effectiveness.”*(ES_11, F1, 14, 3°)

- **ES_14** – *Students involved in GSD training programs usually experience a lack of motivation, schedule problems and communication difficulties, and this is greater still when language differences are present.*”(ES_14, F1, 185, 1°)
- **ES_16** – *“... the architect and designers had cultural differences and could not communicate with each other effectively especially since physical distance between subproject participants prevented informal communication.”* (ES_16, F1, 351, 2°)
- **ES_20** – *“People in remote locations most often have different work cultures and it sometimes becomes difficult to adjust.”*(ES_20, F1, 6, 2°)

F2. Geographical Dispersion

- **ES_03** – *“Geographic dispersion makes it hard the communication about requirements.”* (ES_03, F2, 2, 1°)
- **ES_04** – *“... it is quite possible that a message is misunderstood by one or more of the outsourcing parties. In addition due to the geographical distributed teams in outsourcing business, face-a-face communication is not possible where one can clarify any misunderstanding. These findings indicate that outsourcing clients are aware of the barriers that can undermine the whole outsourcing process.”*(ES_04, F2, 83, 6°)
- **ES_05** – *“Spatial distribution complicates the project manager’s ability to monitor participants and progress.”* (ES_05, F2, 511, 2°)
- **ES_11** – *“Temporal, geographical and socio-cultural distances inherent to DSD seem to exacerbate communication and coordination problems.”* (ES_11, F2, 14, 2°)
- **ES_12** – *“...geographically distributed work teams cannot exchange information through social and informal mechanisms.”* (ES_12, F2, 397, 7°)
- **ES_15** – *“Distance hampers informal communication across sites, making it difficult to disseminate implicit knowledge. This affects both the shared understanding about issues like requirements, and the level of trust accorded to remote teams.”*(ES_15, F2, 72, 9°)
- **ES_18** – *“The challenge that arises with geographical distance is that team members can hardly meet each other face to face. Thus the quality or richness in communication is also reduced.”* (ES_18, F2, 58, 4°)

F3. Language/Language Barriers

- **ES_03** – *“Lack of collaboration between distributed stakeholders happen due to differences in culture, language, distance and processes.”* (ES_03, F3, 2, 3°)

- **ES_04** – *“Due to different cultures and languages in outsourcing business it is quite possible that a message is misunderstood by one or more of the outsourcing parties.”* (ES_04, F3, 83, 6°)
- **ES_05** – *“Language barriers arise in cross national projects when sites and participants do not share a common language or norms of communication resulting in misinterpretations and uncovered information.”* (ES_05, F3, 513, 2°)
- **ES_11** – *“Cultural differences, issues of trust, differences in knowledge levels, and language barriers are cited as causes of poor or ineffective communication, as well as the lack of synchronous communication. Too much information generated by e-mail and frequent conference calls was also identified as source of low effectiveness.”*(ES_11, F3, 14, 3°)
- **ES_14** – *“Students involved in GSD training programs usually experience a lack of motivation, schedule problems and communication difficulties, and this is greater still when language differences are present.”*(ES_14, F3, 185, 1°)
- **ES_15** – *“English has become the lingua franca of global software development. This affects not only the quality of communication, but the choice of communication media.”*(ES_15, F3, 72, 4°)
- **ES_18** – *“Language difference is often mentioned as one of the challenges in communication caused by socio-culture distance. Misinterpretation of message often happen when two communicating parties conversing using foreign language.”* (ES_18, F3, 60, 2°)

F4. Time distance

- **ES_05** – *“Additionally, different time zones may make it difficult to organize conferences. These factors make it challenging to benefit from conferences.”*(ES_05, F4, 514, 2°)
- **ES_06** – *“... it is very difficult to conduct such a long meeting if the distributed teams experience significant time zone differences.”* (ES_06, F4, 179, 3°)
- **ES_11** – *“Time zone differences impact the scheduling and proper running of meetings among sites, as noted in one of the primary studies: “working across a large number of time zones was an enormous issue...this makes it very difficult to schedule meetings, as every time is inconvenient for someone.”* (ES_11, F4, 15, 2°)
- **ES_15** – *“One consequence of temporal distance is delay in response to asynchronous communication.”*(ES_15, F4, 72, 3°)
- **ES_18** – *“Delayed communication feedback is another challenge cause by temporal distance.”* (ES_18, F4, 58, 3°)

F5. Coordination

- **ES_02** – *“Coordination in multisite developments becomes more difficult in terms of articulation work, as problems derived from communication, lack of group awareness, and the complexity of the organization appear which influence the way in which the work must be structured and managed.”* (ES_02, F5, 7, 3°)
- **ES_05** – *“High task coupling between task segments increases the need for intersite communication, coordination, and integration, and it can lead to lower level of performance as well as increase the number of failures.”* (ES_05, F5, 510, 6°)
- **ES_09** – *“A good contract, good communication, coordination and cooperation between all parties build trust and reduce uncertainty for the outsourcing client.”* (ES_09, F5, 5, 7°)
- **ES_16** – *“When Interfaces are developed, Coordination Strategies are required to coordinate the Distributed Teams in order to manage architectural dependencies among tasks. This means that Coordination Strategies are essential for allowing Distributed Teams to communicate and share knowledge when component Interfaces are developed.”* (ES_16, F5, 349, 4°)
- **ES_18** – *“Furthermore hindrance in sharing knowledge and information can influence the frequency of coordination which can lead to poor deliverables and possible rework.”* (ES_18, F5, 63, 3°)

F6. Visibility / Perception

- **ES_02** – *“Developers need to have as much information as possible at their disposal, and to know the full status of the project and its past history, which will in turn allow them to create realistic assumptions about the project. Frequent changes in processes, lack of continuity in communications, and lack of collaborative tool integration cause remote groups to be unaware of what is important because they do not know what other people are working.”* (ES_02, F6, 6, 5°)
- **ES_03** – *“In DSD environments, it’s hard to establish common goals, due to the problems in communication and lack of common understanding. This can cause different viewpoints and priorities on development process.”* (ES_03, F6, 2, 4°)
- **ES_11** – *“There is a requirement for continuous visibility into the team’s activities and operation at all locations. Team members not being informed of the status of remote colleagues progress.”* (ES_11, F6, 3, 2°)

- **ES_12** – “...changes on requirements are normally reported with delay and then to others than relevant stakeholders.” (ES_12, F6, 397, 7°)
- **ES_18** – “... lack of equally shared knowledge can lead to another challenge, i.e. maintaining transparency of project status.” (ES_18, F6, 67, 3°)

F7. Limited Informal Communication

- **ES_02** – “Project and Process Management, high organizational complexity, scheduling, task assignment, and cost estimation become more problematic in distributed environments as a result of volatile requirements, changing specifications, and the lack of informal communication.” (ES_02, F7, 7, 12°)
- **ES_03** – “...the lack of informal communication negatively impacts relationship building.” (ES_03, F7, 2, 1°)
- **ES_05** – “Personal communication is often impeded by absence of informal communication and lack of face-a-face interaction. This can negatively impact trust, decision quality, creativity and general management. Furthermore it may reduce participants’ project overview, which can lead to errors and misunderstandings.” (ES_05, F7, 514, 2°)
- **ES_15** – “Lack of implicit knowledge resulting from limited informal communication means processes like change management, if not explicitly and thoroughly defined, can be applied differently at different sites.” (ES_15, F7, 73, 3°)
- **ES_16** – “... the architect and designers had cultural differences and could not communicate with each other effectively especially since physical distance between subproject participants prevented informal communication.” (ES_16, F7, 351, 2°)
- **ES_18** – “Team members who are separated by distance can hardly have “small-talk” with each other as part of informal communication. They do not have the privilege to have small discussions with each other during coffee break. Furthermore it is difficult for them to develop interpersonal relationships, because most of the times they never even meet with each other.” (ES_18, F7, 58, 5°)

F8. Infrastructure

- **ES_02** – “... the complex infrastructure and the great size of personal networks which change over time, are summarized in a decrease in communication frequency and quality, which directly affects productivity.” (ES_02, F8, 5, 2°)

- **ES_05** – *“Unreliable networks may lead to frustration and low efficiency limit exchange of sensitive information or even cause production stop.”* (ES_05, F8, 514, 3°)
- **ES_06** – *“A lack of dedicated meeting room for each site and Scrum team distribution at multiple sites also appear to be challenging factors that restrict the team communication and collaboration processes.”*(ES_06, F8, 179, 3°)
- **ES_11** – *“IT infrastructure and dedicated office space for meetings are also important challenges due to the need for specific infrastructure to support the distributed work in addition the normal needs of each site.”*(ES_11, F8, 15,2°)
- **ES_15** – *“A project with multiple distributed teams introduces the possibility of multiple, incompatible data repositories, which has a risk of data loss when transferring from one repository to another.”* (ES_15, F8, 74, 4°)

F9. Absence of face-to-face interaction

- **ES_04** – *“... it is quite possible that a message is misunderstood by one or more of the outsourcing parties. In addition due to the geographical distributed teams in outsourcing business, face-a-face communication is not possible where one can clarify any misunderstanding. These findings indicate that outsourcing clients are aware of the barriers that can undermine the whole outsourcing process.”* (ES_04, F2, 83, 6°)
- **ES_05** – *“Lack of frequent face-a-face interaction may impair relationship building since relations are build through communication between project stakeholders.”* (ES_05, F9, 513, 4°)
- **ES_15** – *“The lack of informal face-a-face meetings means team members have less opportunity to form personal relationships that improve trust among individuals.”* (ES_15, F9, 72, 8°)
- **ES_18** – *“Trust is also an issue that arises in distributed teams. It also becomes more difficult for team members to develop a sense of “teamness” because the team members hardly meet each other. The issues of developing trust and sense of teamness can be traced back to the lack of face-a-face meetings.”* (ES_18, F9, 58, 3°)
- **ES_20** – *“It sometimes takes longer to get information / decisions / agreements when you’re not face to face”.* (ES_20, F7, 7,1°)

F10. Definition of Communication Media (synchronous and asynchronous)

- **ES_03** – *“...that synchronous tools should be used for requirements negotiation and asynchronous tools are valuable to structure the discussions before these negotiations.”* (ES_03, F10, 3, 4°)
- **ES_05** – *“If reduction of temporal distance is impossible, the project manager should manage time translations and time adjustments, relocate time using asynchronous media, and institute time-based norms for communication and virtual presence.”* (ES_05, F10, 514, 6°)
- **ES_15** – *“Synchronous communication technology such as video conferencing attempts to replicate the rich interaction present in face-a-face meetings, and is seen as the best solution for meetings in which reaching agreement is the objective.”* (ES_15, F10, 74, 3°)
- **ES_18** – *“Usage of asynchronous communication tools, such as email or voice mail, increases the possibility of ambiguity of information.”* (ES_18, F10, 58, 2°)

F11. Applying Agile Approaches

- **ES_07** – *“Although distributed software development typically relies on formal mechanisms, there is a growing trend towards balancing agile and distributed approaches to meet the challenges of communication, control and trust.”* (ES_07, F11, 106, 1°)
- **ES_16** – *“Initially the adopted communication between an architect in the headquarters (central site) and other members of the project was through emails. The architect received large volumes of emails which could cause bottlenecks. To solve this problem, in the last phases of the project, they adopted SCRUM, an agile development method. Using this method, the architect met in a conference call once each week with managers and group leaders in distributed teams.”* (ES_16, F11, 350, 8°)
- **ES_18** – *“Specifically the Scrum method was found to improve communication between dispersed teams due to members being able to participate and communicate through technologies such as web pages.”* (ES_18, F11, 69, 4°)
- **ES_19** – *“In many studies that we reviewed, agile practices had been customized and a modified agile method was applied. The motivations for these adjustments were reported to be distribution type, overlapping working hours or other factors depending on the situational requirements of the project.”* (ES_19 F11, 8, 1°)

F12. Selection of Communication Technologies

- **ES_02** – *“All the members involved must be able to work with several tools, and the human factor takes on more importance; the team members’ communication skills are a critical factor.”* (ES_02, F12, 6, 3°)
- **ES_05** – *“Being separated, interaction media becomes the primary communication link between sites, but their properties or use may cause loss of contextual information sharing.”* (ES_05, F12, 514, 2°)
- **ES_08** – *“the use of communication technologies, such as e-mail, phone, and video conference evolve over time as the team becomes more mature, and suggested that there could be a sequence of steps in this evolution.”* (ES_08, F12, 787, 10°)
- **ES_18** – *“Usage of appropriate tools is also significant in GSD projects. It is important to ensure that the appropriate tools are used in the project. Appropriate tools not only refer to its use but also other aspects, such as licensing”.* (ES_18, F12, 62, 2°)

F13. Task Distribution

- **ES_02** – *“Project and Process Management, high organizational complexity, scheduling, task assignment, and cost estimation become more problematic in distributed environments as a result of volatile requirements, changing specifications, and the lack of informal communication.”* (ES_02, F13, 7, 12°)
- **ES_05** – *“High task coupling between task segments increases the need for intersite communication, coordination, and integration, and it can lead to lower level of performance as well as increase the number of failures.”* (ES_05, F13, 510, 6°)
- **ES_16** – *“When Interfaces are developed, Coordination Strategies are required to coordinate the Distributed Teams in order to manage architectural dependencies among tasks. This means that Coordination Strategies are essential for allowing Distributed Teams to communicate and share knowledge when component Interfaces are developed.”* (ES_16, F13, 349, 4°)
- **ES_18** – *“Selecting the appropriate activity distribution model is one of the most challenging challenges tasks in GSD projects. Deciding which activities to be distributed and how they are distributed can determine the success and failures of the project.”*(ES_18, F13, 62, 1°)

F14. Collaboration Tools

- **ES_02** – *“... the need for user-friendly tools, and integrate collaborative tools and agents to improve knowledge integration.”* (ES_02, F14, 5, 2°)

- **ES_06** – *“An enterprise wiki (e.g. Confluence) has been found to be very effective while using Scrum practices. Distributed team members can communicate and publish the results of various Scrum meetings minutes in wiki.”* (ES_06, F14, 181, 2°)
- **ES_14** – *“... to interact with partners of different cultures, by using several types of communication tools: Mailing lists, emails and chats; Wikis (each sub-team in the project maintained a wiki containing all the documents and artifacts that they produced); Blogs (in which the students reflected their weekly progress in the project).”* (ES_14, F14, 183, 10°)
- **ES_18** – *“Communication and collaborative tools are essential to the success of software development projects. The effectiveness of communication between sites that are separated geographically is dependent on the appropriateness of the tools and the quality of the tools utilized.”* (ES_18, F14, 69, 2°)

F15. High Bandwidth

- **ES_05** – *“Include speed and quality in the communication media requirements as well as stability and reliability.”* (ES_05, F15, 529, 5°)
- **ES_06** – *“Providing better communication bandwidth and right tool in a distributed project that use distributed Scrum meeting practices is vital. Scrum team can choose appropriate tool from a wide range of communication tools suitable to the communication bandwidth.”* (ES_06, F15, 179, 4°)

F16. Communication Standards

- **ES_02** – *“The software life cycle requires a great deal of communication between those members involved in the development who exchange a large amount of information through different tools and different formats without following communication standards, and who thus face misunderstandings and high response times.”* (ES_02, F16, 461, 3°)
- **ES_05** – *“...participants do not share a common language or norms of communication resulting in misinterpretations and uncovered information.”* (ES_05, F16, 513, 2°)

F17. Team awareness

- **ES_02** – *“Coordination in multisite developments becomes more difficult in terms of articulation work, as problems derived from communication, lack of group awareness, and the complexity of the organization appear which influence the way in which the work must be structured and managed.”* (ES_02, F17, 7, 3°)

- **ES_13** – *“Dispersed software teams do not get information on what other teams are doing, so it is difficult to know the traceability of each module and the definition of modifications or problems to be handled is unclear. These issues are classified as group awareness problems, where group awareness is defined as an understanding of the activities of others]. Group awareness provides team members with important information that can ensure smooth collaboration.”* (ES_13, F17, 4, 5°)

F18. Communication skills

- **ES_02** – *“The security of communications must also be taken into account. All the members involved must be able to work with several tools, and the human factor takes on more importance; the team members’ communication skills are a critical factor.”* (ES_02, F18, 6, 4°)
- **ES_18** – *“Knowledge and information sharing often becomes an issue in GSD projects. Sometimes the reluctance to share information is because of linguistic differences and lack of communication skills.”* (ES_18, F18, 63, 3°)

F19. Contact Networks

ES_02 – *“The great size of personal networks which change over time, are summarized in a decrease in communication frequency and quality, which directly affects productivity.”* (ES_02, F19, 5, 2°)

- **ES_17** – *“... redes de contato no trabalho distribuído serem muito menores quando comparadas às co-localizadas e com menor frequência de comunicação, pois o número médio de diferentes pessoas contactadas em uma semana por equipes localmente localizadas é de 16.0, enquanto que, no contexto distribuído, alcança-se apenas 4.9 contatos.”* (ES_17, F19, 5, 3°)

F20. Definition of Roles and Responsibilities

- **ES_18** – *“With limited chances to see each other due to geographical distance, there is occasional confusion of roles and responsibilities among distributed team members.”* (ES_18, F20, 61, 3°)

F21. Synchronization of Working Hours

- **ES_06** – *“Scrum teams to ensure synchronous communication among distributed sites can be arranged. This is done by adjusting working hours, working from home, working long hours and so on.”* (ES_06, F21, 179, 8°)

F22. Number of Distributed Teams

- **ES_01** – *“The complexity of communication, coordination and control in GSE projects is dependent on the number of distributed sites. Increasing the number of collaboration partners increases the number of sources of threat and also complexity of trust achievement.”* (ES_01, F22, 2, 2°)

F23. Communication Policies

- **ES_06** – *“Scrum teams also use strict communication policy (e.g. E-mail reply within 12 hours) to avoid delay due to the temporal distance of a distributed team.”* (ES_06, F23, 180, 2°)

F24. Different Styles of Communication

- **ES_03** – *“Differing attitudes and communication styles often result in stakeholders’ misinterpretation and difficulties to understand the requirements, particularly when they are from different organizations, with different work environments.”* (ES_03, F24, 2, 5°)

F25. Collaboration Models

- **ES_10** – *“The NextMove project model allows the task coordination problem to be described in a more formal manner. Based on the NextMove framework, the NextMove distributed project management tool aims to help project teams in tracking, coordinating and communicating tasks in a distributed development environment.”* (ES_10, F25, 3, 1°)

F26. Multiple Communication Channels

- **ES_06** – *“To provide a rich communication environment and also to avoid slow, unreliable, and poor transmission, Scrum teams use the practice “multiple communication mode.”* (ES_06, F26, 180, 11°)

F27. Size of Personal Networks

- **ES_02** – *“...combined with the complex infrastructure and the great size of personal networks which change over time, are summarized in a decrease in communication frequency and quality, which directly affects productivity.”* (ES_02, F27, 5, 2°)

F28. Translation and Coding Processes

- **ES_02** – “*The use of translation processes and codification guidelines is therefore useful, because different levels of understanding of the problem domain also exist, as do different levels of knowledge, skills, and training between teams.*” (ES_02, F28, 6, 2°)

F29. Weak Social Relations

- **ES_05** – “*Mutual trust is important but hard to obtain in GDSPs. This can be due to lack of face-a-face interaction cultural differences and weak social relations. Trust among stakeholders is necessary to achieve innovation, flexibility, cooperation, and efficiency in a distributed environment.*” (ES_05, F29, 513, 3°)

Table 2 - Effects of the communication process in DDS by category

Categories	Effects	References – ES: Secondary Studies	Number of Studies (Reviews) (%)
C1. Human Factors	E1. Uncertainties, Misunderstandings and Misconceptions	ES_02; ES_03; ES_04; ES_05; ES_13; ES_15; ES_18;	7/20 (35%)
	E3. Lack of confidence	ES_01; ES_05; ES_07; ES_15; ES_18.	5/20 (25%)
	E8. Personal relationships	ES_04; ES_15; ES_17.	3/20 (15%)
	E21. Lack of Team Cohesion	ES_19.	1/20 (5%)
	E23. Low Creativity	ES_05.	1/20 (5%)
	E25. Team maturation	ES_08.	1/20 (5%)
C2. Location and Infrastructure	E14. Collaboration between Teams	ES_05; ES_15.	2/20 (10%)
	E16. Absence of Synchronous Communication	ES_06; ES_11.	2/20 (10%)
	E18. High Number of Failures	ES_05; ES_18.	2/20 (10%)
	E22. Low performance	ES_05.	1/20 (5%)
C3. Processos e Tecnologias	E2. Limited Information Sharing	ES_02; ES_05; ES_12; ES_13; ES_18; ES_20;	6/20 (30%)
	E4. Communication Quality	ES_05; ES_06; ES_13; ES_15.	4/20 (20%)
	E5. Response delay	ES_02; ES_05; ES_15; ES_18.	4/20 (20%)

E6. Requirements Gathering Process	ES_03; ES_08; ES_17.	3/20 (15%)
E7. Knowledge Sharing	ES_02; ES_05; ES_17.	3/20 (15%)
E9. Ambiguity of Information	ES_02; ES_17; ES_18.	3/20 (15%)
E10. Distributed Project Management	ES_02; ES_19.	2/20 (10%)
E11. Productivity reduction	ES_02; ES_05.	2/20 (10%)
E12. Software Defects	ES_02; ES_05.	2/20 (10%)
E13. Communication Frequency Reduction	ES_02; ES_17.	2/20 (10%)
E15. Loss of Information	ES_05; ES_19.	2/20 (10%)
E17. Project Success	ES_05; ES_18.	2/20 (10%)
E19. Regular Feedback Using Scrum	ES_06; ES_18.	2/20 (10%)
E20. Communication restriction	ES_06.	1/20 (5%)
E24. Low Quality of Decision	ES_05.	1/20 (5%)

Source: Own Preparation, with data from the tertiary study

E1. Uncertainties, Misunderstandings and Misconceptions

- **ES_02** – *“Cultural differences imply different terminologies which may cause mistakes in messages and translation errors.”* (ES_02, F1, 6, 2°)
- **ES_03** – *“Differing attitudes and communication styles often result in stakeholders’ misinterpretation and difficulties to understand the requirements, particularly when they are from different organizations, with different work environments.”* (ES_03, F24, 2, 5°)
- **ES_04** – *“... it is quite possible that a message is misunderstood by one or more of the outsourcing parties. In addition due to the geographical distributed teams in outsourcing business, face-a-face communication is not possible where one can clarify any misunderstanding. These findings indicate that outsourcing clients are aware of the barriers that can undermine the whole outsourcing process.”* ((ES_04, F2, 83, 6°); (ES_04, F9, 83, 6°))
- **ES_05** – *“Task uncertainty represents lack of information needed to develop the software. High equivocality increases coordination and communication needs and demands on interaction media.”* (ES_05, E1, 510, 6°)

- **ES_13** – *“However, a lack of real-time awareness can still lead to misunderstandings.”* (ES_13, E1, 5, 2°)
- **ES_15** – *“Lack of informal communication also limits process visibility, leading to misunderstandings and frustration on the part of remote teams.”* (ES_15, E1, 73, 3°)
- **ES_18** – *“Language difference is often mentioned as one of the challenges in communication caused by socio-culture distance. Misinterpretation of message often happen when two communicating parties conversing using foreign language.”* (ES_18, F3, 60, 2°).

E2. Limited Information Sharing

- **ES_02** – *“The software life cycle requires a great deal of communication between those members involved in the development who exchange a large amount of information through different tools and different formats without following communication standards, and who thus face misunderstandings and high response times.”* (ES_02, F16, 461, 3°)
- **ES_05** – *“Unreliable networks may lead to frustration and low efficiency, limit exchange of sensitive information or even cause production stop.”* (ES_05, F8, 514, 3°)
- **ES_12** – *“...geographically distributed work teams cannot exchange information through social and informal mechanisms.”* (ES_12, E2, 397, 7°)
- **ES_13** – *“Dispersed software teams do not get information on what other teams are doing, so it is difficult to know the traceability of each module and the definition of modifications or problems to be handled is unclear.”* (ES_13, F17, 4, 5°)
- **ES_18** – *“Sometimes the provided information to the remote team is insufficient, thus leading to rework. Ensuring proper flow of information is almost as important and challenging as ensuring equal access to information. Communication bottleneck can cause delays.”* (ES_18, E2, 63, 2°)
- **ES_20** – *“It sometimes takes longer to get information / decisions / agreements when you’re not face to face”.* (ES_20, F9, 7,1°)

E3. Lack of confidence

- **ES_01** – *“The complexity of communication, coordination and control in GSE projects is dependent on the number of distributed sites. Increasing the number of collaboration partners increases the number of sources of threat and also complexity of trust achievement.”* (ES_01, F22, 2, 2°)

- **ES_05** – *“Mutual trust is important but hard to obtain in GDSPs. This can be due to lack of face-a-face interaction cultural differences and weak social relations. Trust among stakeholders is necessary to achieve innovation, flexibility, cooperation, and efficiency in a distributed environment.”* ((ES_05, F1, 513, 3°), (ES_05, F29, 513, 3°))
- **ES_07** – *“Although distributed software development typically relies on formal mechanisms, there is a growing trend towards balancing agile and distributed approaches to meet the challenges of communication, control and trust.”* (ES_07, F11, 106, 1°)
- **ES_15** – *“Distance hampers informal communication across sites, making it difficult to disseminate implicit knowledge. This affects both the shared understanding about issues like requirements, and the level of trust accorded to remote teams.”*(ES_15, F2, 72, 9°)
- **ES_18** – *“Trust is also an issue that arises in distributed teams. It also becomes more difficult for team members to develop a sense of “teamness” because the team members hardly meet each other. The issues of developing trust and sense of teamness can be traced back to the lack of face-a-face meetings.”* (ES_18, F9, 58, 3°)

E4. Communication Quality

- **ES_05** – *“Include speed and quality in the communication media requirements as well as stability and reliability.”* (ES_05, F15, 529, 5°)
- **ES_06** – *“To provide a rich communication environment and also to avoid slow, unreliable, and poor transmission, Scrum teams use the practice “multiple communication modes.”* (ES_06, F26, 180, 11°)
- **ES_13** – *“Team members also can establish group mailing lists and use instant messenger tools to improve communication between individuals.”* (ES_13, E4, 5, 3°)
- **ES_15** – *“Communication technology is the most commonly cited approach to the geographic distance problem. Synchronous communication technology such as video conferencing attempts to replicate the rich interaction present in faceto-face meetings, and is seen as the best solution for meetings in which reaching agreement is the objective.”* (ES_15, E4, 74, 4°)

E5. Response delay

- **ES_02** – *“The software life cycle requires a great deal of communication between those members involved in the development who exchange a large amount of information through different tools and different formats without following communication standards, and who thus face misunderstandings and high response times.”* (ES_02, F16, 461, 3°)
- **ES_05** – *“Temporal distribution increases the complexity of planning and coordination activities, makes multisite virtual meetings hard to plan causes unproductive waits, delays feedback, and complicates simple things like time referencing and time settings.”* (ES_05, E5,511, 2°)
- **ES_15** – *“Delayed response to communication is seen as a barrier to developing ‘familiarity’ among participants, which in turn is seen as an impediment to developing trust.”* (ES_15, E5, 72, 8°)
- **ES_18** – *“The challenges in other process areas that can also be associated with control include planning appropriate activities distribution (coordination) and delayed communication feedback (communication).”* (ES_18, E5, 64, 2°)

E6. Requirements Gathering Process

- **ES_03** – *“... synchronous tools should be used for requirements negotiation and asynchronous tools are valuable to structure the discussions before these negotiations.”*(ES_03, E6, 3, 4°)
- **ES_08** – *“... address the importance of communication for the Requirements Engineering process within globally distributed teams. They claimed that the use of communication technologies, such as e-mail, phone, and video conference.”* (ES_08, E6, 787, 10°)
- **ES_17** – *“... a vídeo-conferência torna-se mais eficaz na busca de um acordo mútuo em momentos de negociação de requisitos, com possibilidade até destas discussões em momentos assíncronos servirem de pauta para reuniões síncronas.”* (ES_17, E6, 6, 3°)

E7. Knowledge Sharing

- **ES_02** – *“... discuss the need for user-friendly tools, and integrate collaborative tools and agents to improve knowledge integration.”* (ES_02, E7, 5, 2°)
- **ES_05** – *“Knowledge capture is especially important when dissolving the project since it may be difficult to subsequently locate a person who possesses the needed knowledge.”* (ES_05, E7, 511, 1°)

- **ES_16** – *“When Interfaces are developed, Coordination Strategies are required to coordinate the Distributed Teams in order to manage architectural dependencies among tasks. This means that Coordination Strategies are essential for allowing Distributed Teams to communicate and share knowledge when component Interfaces are developed.”* ((ES_16, F5, 349, 4°), (ES_16, F13, 349, 4°))

E8. Personal relationships

- **ES_04** – *“Understanding different factors in managing software development outsourcing relationships can help to ensure the long lasting relationships between clients and vendors.”* (ES_04, E8, 82, 10°)
- **ES_15** – *“The most common approach to developing trust among global software developers is to arrange face-to-face meetings, either via video conference or via in-person. This allows team members to form personal relationships.”* (ES_15, E8, 75, 6°)

E9. Ambiguity of Information

- **ES_02** – *“Supported by collaborative tools, which are a means of avoiding ambiguity and face-a-face meetings without comprising the quality of the results.”* (ES_02, E9, 5, 2°)
- **ES_18** – *“Usage of asynchronous communication tools, such as email or voice mail, increases the possibility of ambiguity of information.”* (ES_18, F10, 58, 2°)

E10. Distributed Project Management

- **ES_02** – *“Establishment of an efficient communication mechanism between the members of the organization, allowing a developer to discover the status and changes made within each project.”* (ES_02, E10,10, 1°)
- **ES_19** – *“... lack of equally shared knowledge can lead to another challenge, i.e. maintaining transparency of project status.”* (ES_19, F10, 67, 3°)

E11. Productivity reduction

- **ES_02** – *The great size of personal networks which change over time, are summarized in a decrease in communication frequency and quality, which directly affects productivity.”* ((ES_02, F19, 5, 2°) (ES_02, F27, 5, 2°))

- **ES_05** – *“Unreliable networks may lead to frustration and low efficiency limit exchange of sensitive information or even cause production stop.”* (ES_05, F8, 514, 3°)

E12. Software Defects

- **ES_02** – *“Software defects become more frequent due to the added complexity, and in most cases, this is related to communication problems and a lack of group awareness.”* (ES_02, E12, 58, 2°)
- **ES_05** – *“... knowledge capture may be limited in GDSPs due to factors such as changing relations and roles across the organization, properties of electronic communication media and lacking knowledge of different sites. This results in reduced capability to discover defects in the developed software or loss of knowledge about options or specific problem solutions.”* (ES_05, E12, 511, 1°)

E13. Communication Frequency Reduction

- **ES_02** – *“... the complex infrastructure and the great size of personal networks which change over time, are summarized in a decrease in communication frequency and quality, which directly affects productivity.”* (ES_02, F8, 5, 2°)

E14. Team collaboration

- **ES_05** – *“Collaboration capability describes the project participants’ understanding and appreciation of differences in competencies and their ability to effectively use technology to gather and share information across geographical and functional distances.”* (ES_05, E14, 511, 3°)
- **ES_15** – *“In addition to communication media, a common set of tools shared by all sites, including a configuration management system that stores design documents and meeting minutes, as well as source code, facilitates collaboration.”* (ES_15, E14, 74, 9°)

E15. Loss of Information

- **ES_05** – *“Being separated, interaction media becomes the primary communication link between sites, but their properties or use may cause loss of contextual information sharing.”* (ES_05, F6, 514, 2°)
- **ES_19** – *“Another communication issue caused by geographical distance is loss of data during transfer due to differences in tools. Sometimes data loss can also be caused by usage of different tools.”* (ES_19, E15, 59, 4°)

E16. Absence of Synchronous Communication

- **ES_06** – *“Usually sprint planning or retrospective sessions can last up to four hours or sometimes even more. Thus, it is very difficult to conduct such a long meeting if the distributed teams experience significant time zone differences. For this reason, lack of synchronous communication is considered as one of the most vital challenges for using Scrum in GSD context.”* (ES_06, E16, 179, 3^o)
- **ES_11** – *“Cultural differences, issues of trust, differences in knowledge levels, and language barriers are cited as causes of poor or ineffective communication, as well as the lack of synchronous communication. Too much information generated by e-mail and frequent conference calls was also identified as source of low effectiveness.”*(ES_11, F1, 14, 3^o)

E17. Project Success

- **ES_05** – *“... selection of appropriate information and communication technology is crucial for project success.”* (ES_05, E17, 462, 3^o)
- **ES_18** – *“Communication and collaborative tools are essential to the success of software development projects.”* (ES_18, E17, 69, 2^o)

E18. High Number of Failures

- **ES_05** – *“High task coupling between task segments increases the need for intersite communication, coordination, and integration, and it can lead to lower level of performance as well as increase the number of failures.”* (ES_05, F5, 510, 6^o) (ES_05, F13, 510, 6^o)
- **ES_18** – *“Selecting the appropriate activity distribution model is one of the most challenging challenges tasks in GSD projects. Deciding which activities to be distributed and how they are distributed can determine the success and failures of the project.”* (ES_18, F13, 62, 1^o)

E19. Regular Feedback Using Scrum

- **ES_06** – *“Scrum teams also use strict communication policy (e.g. E-mail reply within 12 hours) to avoid delay due to the temporal distance of a distributed team.”* (ES_06, F23, 180, 2^o)
- **ES_18** – *“Agile methods encourage the need for frequent communication and regular feedbacks due to their highly flexible and unpredictable change to work documents such as requirements specifications.”* (ES_18, E19, 69, 3^o)

E20. Communication restriction

- **ES_06** – *“A lack of dedicated meeting room for each site and Scrum team distribution at multiple sites also appear to be challenging factors that restrict the team communication and collaboration processes.”* (ES_06, F8, 179, 3°)

E21. Lack of Team Cohesion

- **ES_19** – *“... combining agile practices with a global or distributed context complicates things even further, which may decrease a team’s cohesion.”* (ES_19, E21, 1, 3°)

E22. Low performance

- **ES_05** – *“High task coupling between task segments increases the need for intersite communication, coordination, and integration, and it can lead to lower level of performance as well as increase the number of failures.”* (ES_05, F5, 510, 6°) (ES_05, F13, 510, 6°)

E23. Low Creativity

- **ES_05** – *“Personal communication is often impeded by absence of informal communication and lack of face-a-face interaction. This can negatively impact trust, decision quality, creativity and general management. Furthermore it may reduce participants’ project overview, which can lead to errors and misunderstandings.”* (ES_05, F7, 514, 2°)

E24. Low Quality of Decision

- **ES_05** – *“Personal communication is often impeded by absence of informal communication and lack of face-a-face interaction. This can negatively impact trust, decision quality, creativity and general management. Furthermore it may reduce participants’ project overview, which can lead to errors and misunderstandings.”* (ES_05, F7, 514, 2°)

E25. Team maturation

- **ES_08** – *“... the use of communication technologies, such as e-mail, phone, and video conference evolve over time as the team becomes more mature, and*

suggested that there could be a sequence of steps in this evolution." (ES_08, F12, 787, 10°)